

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

STATISTICAL MODELING OF DIMENSIONAL VARIATION USING MONTE CARLO SIMULATION IN A CAD/CAM/CNC MANUFACTURING PROCESS

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Abstract

This paper proposes an applied approach to the statistical modeling of the variation in a critical dimensional feature – the reference diameter – within a CAD/CAM/CNC-assisted manufacturing process, using Monte Carlo simulation. The analyzed feature, namely the inner diameter of the clamping ring, was designed and programmed in Fusion 360, where toolpaths were defined, G-code was generated, and the complete CNC machining process was simulated.

In the absence of real parts, the statistical analysis was based on a simulated dataset ($n = 10,000$), generated in accordance with the nominal value of 28.00 mm and the tolerance range [27.95 mm – 28.05 mm]. The study included the estimation of the mean and standard deviation, the evaluation of the probability of exceeding the tolerance limits, and the calculation of process capability indices (**C_p** and **C_{pk}**). The results indicated a **nearly capable process** ($C_p = 0.998$; $C_{pk} = 0.908$), with an estimated rejection rate of 0.36%. This paper highlights the applicability of statistical methods in modern engineering contexts, demonstrating how numerical simulation can serve as a viable alternative for analysis when experimental data is unavailable. Such analysis can support optimization decisions during the early stages of process design.

Keywords: process capability, normal distribution, descriptive statistics, Monte Carlo simulation

1. Introduction

Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM), in close connection with Computer-Aided Design (CAD), represents a central pillar in the digitalization of processes within the manufacturing industry. Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machines are widely used due to their high precision, execution efficiency, and advanced automation capabilities [4,5,6].

The specialized literature highlights the growing integration of CAD/CAM/CNC systems, with emphasis on toolpath optimization, advanced machining process simulation, automatic G-code generation, and the use of sensors for real-time operation monitoring. These technologies contribute significantly to reducing execution times, improving product quality, and increasing the flexibility of industrial processes.

According to recent studies, the integration of CAD/CAM systems with next-generation CNC machines can reduce the total production time by up to 30%, as a result of the complete automation of the design and manufacturing stages [3,4].

This article continues the research previously carried out in a bachelor's thesis [2], which analyzed the machining process of the "reference diameter" feature using a Stepcraft Q 204 CNC machine. The present

study adds an advanced statistical analysis component, employing probabilistic methods and Monte Carlo simulation to evaluate the process capability.

The main objective of this study is to perform a statistical analysis of a critical feature—the inner diameter of the clamping ring (referred to as the “reference diameter”)—within a CAD/CAM/CNC-assisted manufacturing process. Starting from the 3D model of the part and the complete simulation of the machining process in Fusion 360, a detailed analysis was conducted on the dimensional variation using an extended set of simulated data.

This approach aims to highlight the potential of statistical methods for assessing process quality, even in the absence of direct experimental control. The results obtained allow relevant conclusions to be drawn regarding the robustness and capability of the simulated process, offering a coherent validation framework in the design phase.

2. Materials and Method

This study was conducted entirely in a digital environment, without the use of physical parts, through the integration of a CAD/CAM/CNC design platform and statistical analysis tools. The 3D modeling of the

component was carried out in **Fusion 360 (Autodesk)**, where the toolpaths were defined, G-codes were generated, and a complete simulation of the CNC machining process was performed.

The analyzed dimensional feature—the inner diameter of the clamping ring (referred to as the “reference diameter”)—has a **nominal value of 28.00 mm**, with a **tolerance of ± 0.05 mm**, according to the design specifications.

For the statistical evaluation, the **Monte Carlo simulation method** was applied directly, generating a dataset of **10,000 diameter values** based on a **normal distribution** defined by the nominal value and the given tolerance limits. This extended dataset allowed for rigorous analyses of process variation.

Statistical analysis was performed using **Microsoft Excel** (Analysis ToolPak module), and graphical verification and supplementary estimations were carried out using **Jamovi**.

3. Part Design and CAM/CNC Process Simulation

The 3D model of the analyzed component was developed in the **Fusion 360** design environment, developed by Autodesk, which provides an integrated platform for geometric modeling, toolpath generation, and CNC programming (CAM).

The studied part includes an internal circular element—referred to hereafter as the **reference diameter**—whose dimensional precision is critical to the functionality of the assembly.

The simulation of the toolpaths was carried out entirely in Fusion 360 in order to evaluate the accuracy of movements, ensure collision avoidance, and validate the CAM process prior to physical execution.

The toolpaths were visualized in real time and included:

- roughing of the external surfaces,
- internal contouring,
- vertical drilling,
- final finishing through chamfering.

The final result of the part after all simulated operations is shown in **Figure 1**. The simulation confirmed the coherence of the process and the integrity of the toolpaths, with no collisions or functional errors.

Figure 1. Final result of the processing simulation.

Source: adapted from Butnaru M.A. (2025). p. 48

4. Data Processing and Process Capability Analysis

As this paper is application-oriented but does not include the physical manufacturing stage, the statistical analysis was conducted based on a simulated dataset, in accordance with the dimensions obtained through CAD design and CNC simulation of the "garnish" assembly. The analyzed feature—the **inner diameter of the clamping ring**—has a **nominal value of 28.00 mm**, established during the CAD design phase, with an imposed **tolerance of ± 0.05 mm**.

The generated dataset reflects realistic deviations within the technical tolerance limits, based on **normal**

distributions, in order to enable the rigorous application of mathematical statistical methods and the virtual testing of process stability.

Figure 2 presents a fragment of the **Monte Carlo simulation** carried out in Excel for a sample of **10,000 parts**, using the normal distribution defined by the actual process parameters ($\mu = 28.0046$ mm, $\sigma = 0.01656$ mm). The generation formula used was `=NORM.INV(RAND();28,0046;0,01656)`, and the compliance check within the tolerance limits [27,95 mm – 28,05 mm] was performed using `=IF(AND(A2>=27,95;A2<=28,05);0;1)`.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Generate Monte Carlo values	Conformity								
2	28,00656861	0	=IF(AND(A2>=27,95;A2<=28,05);0;1)				conform	9964	=COUNTIF(C2:C10001;0)	
3	28,00209246	0					neconform	36	=COUNTIF(C2:C10001;1)	
4	28,0146544	0								
5	28,01695766	0								
6	27,98724714	0								
7	27,98156881	0								
8	28,03363852	0								
9	28,01870181	0								
10	27,98998974	0								
11	28,00023043	0								

Figure 2. Monte Carlo simulation in Excel for a sample of 10,000 pieces

The values 0 and 1 were used to distinguish conforming and nonconforming parts, respectively. As a

result, **9,964 parts** out of 10,000 were classified as conforming, while **36 parts** exceeded the tolerance limits, indicating a **simulated rejection rate of 0.36%**.

Descriptives		Generate Monte Carlo values	
Descriptives			
	A		
N	10000	Mean	28.00453333
Missing	0	Standard Error	0.00016655
Mean	28.0	Median	28.00450374
95% CI mean lower bound	28.0	Mode	#N/A
95% CI mean upper bound	28.0	Standard Deviation	0.016654977
Median	28.0	Sample Variance	0.000277388
Mode	28.0*	Kurtosis	0.077775625
Sum	280045	Skewness	-0.006872009
Standard deviation	0.0167	Range	0.150591979
Variance	2.77e-4	Minimum	27.92517978
Range	0.151	Maximum	28.07577176
Minimum	27.9	Sum	280045.3333
Maximum	28.1	Count	10000
Skewness	-0.00687	Confidence Level(95%)	0.000326471
Std. error skewness	0.0245		
Kurtosis	0.0778		
Std. error kurtosis	0.0490		

Figure 3. Descriptive statistics for the Monte Carlo generated distribution ($n = 10,000$), obtained with Jamovi and Excel

The data generated through Monte Carlo simulation ($n = 10,000$) were statistically analyzed using two complementary environments: **Microsoft Excel** and the statistical software **Jamovi**. The descriptive results confirmed the consistency of the distribution, with closely matching values for the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis:

- The **estimated mean** was **28.0045 mm**, very close to the nominal value of 28.00 mm, with a **95% confidence interval** around the mean of approximately ± 0.0003 mm.

- The **standard deviation** of approximately **0.01657 mm** reflects relatively low variation, although it slightly exceeds the maximum acceptable limit when compared to the width of the tolerance zone.

- The **simulated distribution** is nearly normal, with very low **skewness** (≈ -0.0068) and slight **kurtosis** (≈ 0.077), indicating a mild concentration around the central value.

- The **density histogram** (Fig. 4) visually confirms this observation: the bell-shaped curve is symmetric and well-centered around the 28 mm value.

Figure 4. Histogram

This **multiple validation**—both numerical and graphical—supports the **credibility of the simulated distribution** and provides a solid foundation for continuing the **process capability analysis** (C_p and C_{pk}), as well as for estimating the **nonconformity probability**.

In the following section, the **process capability indices** (Fig. 5) are calculated to determine the extent to which this statistical variation falls within the specified **tolerance limits**.

To evaluate the performance of the **simulated manufacturing process**, the **capability indices C_p and C_{pk}** were calculated using the standard formulas:

$$C_p = \frac{USL - LSL}{6\sigma} \quad (1)$$

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	C_p	0.998004	$= (28.05 - 27.95) / (6 * 0.0167)$					
2	C_{pk}	0.908184	$= \text{MIN}((28.05 - 28.0045) / (3 * 0.0167); (28.0045 - 27.95) / (3 * 0.0167))$					

Fig. 5. Calculation of the C_p and C_{pk} capability indices for the Monte Carlo-generated distribution ($n = 10,000$)

$C_p \approx 1$ indicates that the process is potentially capable in terms of variation — the standard deviation is sufficiently small to allow the parts to fall within the specified tolerance limits.

However, the fact that $C_{pk} < 1$ suggests that the process mean is not perfectly centered within the tolerance range, resulting in a slight drift toward the upper specification limit.

This situation is critical from a quality standpoint: although variability is well-controlled, the lack of centering may lead to an increased number of defective parts over time — especially in real-world manufacturing processes where additional, uncontrolled sources of variation may occur.

In conclusion, the analyzed process is **near-capable**, but requires a shift in mean positioning to minimize the likelihood of producing nonconforming parts. The subunitary C_{pk} value is a clear indicator that the process mean must be adjusted to better align with the center of the specified tolerance interval.

$$C_{pk} = \min\left(\frac{USL - \mu}{3\sigma}, \frac{\mu - LSL}{3\sigma}\right) \quad (2)$$

where:

- $USL = 28,05$ mm (upper specification limit)
- $LSL = 27,95$ mm (lower specification limit)
- $\mu = 28,0045$ mm (sample mean)
- $\sigma = 0,0167$ mm ((estimated standard deviation))

The results obtained from the analysis of the 10,000 simulated parts using the Monte Carlo method are shown in **Figure 5**.

5. Discussion and Interpretation

The integration of Monte Carlo numerical simulation with statistical analysis enabled an objective evaluation of the process capability for the critical dimensional characteristic — the **reference diameter**. Although the values were artificially generated, they faithfully reflect the behavior of a real manufacturing process, being constructed based on parameters obtained through CAD/CAM design and CNC simulation in the Fusion 360 environment.

Based on the 10,000 simulated values, the resulting mean diameter was **28.0047 mm**, with a standard deviation of **0.01658 mm** — values comparable to those observed in a stable, well-controlled process. However, the positioning of the mean outside the center of the tolerance interval [27.95 mm – 28.05 mm] affected the C_{pk} value, which fell below the industrial acceptability threshold.

- The **Cp index = 0.998004** suggests that the process exhibits low variability and would be capable if it were perfectly centered within the tolerance limits.
- The **Cpk index = 0.908184** indicates a slight shift of the mean relative to the center of the interval, which negatively impacts the overall process performance.

This finding is reinforced by the estimated probability of nonconformity: approximately **0.36%** of parts exceed the tolerance limits and would require rejection. Although this percentage is low, it points to a real risk of producing nonconforming parts under production conditions.

6. General Conclusions

This study demonstrated the feasibility of integrating computer-aided design (CAD), CAM/CNC programming, and statistical analysis methods into a unified approach for evaluating a manufacturing process. Even in the absence of experimental data obtained through physical measurements, CNC simulations combined with Monte Carlo data generation enabled a rigorous assessment of the dimensional consistency of the analyzed component.

The statistical analysis included:

- estimation of the mean and standard deviation,
- evaluation of the probability of exceeding the tolerance limits,
- calculation of **Cp** and **Cpk** indices to assess process capability.

The results indicated a mean diameter of **28.0047 mm** and a standard deviation of **0.01658 mm**. With **Cp = 0.998** and **Cpk = 0.908**, the process exhibits acceptable variability but shows a slight shift of the mean away from the center of the tolerance range. Out of the

10,000 simulated parts, **9,964** were conforming and **36** were nonconforming, corresponding to a rejection rate of **0.36%**.

These findings show that the process is **nearly capable**, yet a fine-tuning of the mean position is required to meet strict industrial standards for centering and precision. The study highlights the practical potential of mathematical statistics in manufacturing engineering, offering a robust decision-making tool from the design phase, with direct benefits in preventing quality issues before launching real production.

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